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Generation of Solid Waste and its Impacts on Environment – A Geographical Study of Meerut City

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Abstract

Urbanisation and industrialisation are the main factors which are responsible to degrade the environmental quality. Population is increasing at alarming rate in the urban areas due to high birth rate and rural to urban migration. Mostly cities are suffering from the problems of solid waste management in India. Meerut city is one of them. Collection, transportation and disposal facilities are not highly developed in Meerut city. There facilities are developed only approved colonies and unauthorized colonies are facing such types of problems. High income group is mostly generator of solid waste than the poor income group people. Residence, roads, streets, daily and weekly markets, industries, hotel and restaurants, marriage halls, institution etc. are the major sources of solid waste generation in the study area. Very few resources have solid waste management system that is suitable for eco-friendly. Mostly generator of solid waste have poor management about it. 'Swatch Bharat Mission' is playing an important role to collect the solid waste and its management in the study area.

Keywords Solid Waste, Generation, Environmental Degradation, Management, Sources, Urbanisation.

Introduction Solid waste management is a big challenge for the developing countries now a days. These countries have a lot of population of the world and are suffering from the solid waste generation problem. Solid waste generation is related to the over population growth because to fulfill their requirement the maximum resources are used here. Pollution, land degradation, climate change, public health issues, animals health issues etc. are the major impact on the environment of the solid waste. Open and unsanitary landfills contribute to contamination of drinking water and can cause infection and transmit diseases. Generation of the solid waste amount have a big difference between poor and rich families because the rich families use maximum resources due to high income group and high expenditure level. Poor families have not sufficient budget for the qualitative and quantitative essential requirement of the daily uses products. These families are poor due to unemployment and lowest wages. At present hotel, restaurant, marriage hall etc. are becoming a status of symbol in the society. So these resources are generating a huge amount of solid waste. On the observation of these resources in the context of solid waste generation mostly people waste the food and waste the resources like that water bottles, napkins, spoons, disposal glasses etc. These resources are collected all such types of wastes but have not treatment facilities. So untreated such types of waste is very harmful to the environment and create the environmental problems. Not only human beings are effected by the untreated solid waste but also birds, animals and vegetations are effected by its. A high death rate of the animals is found here due to eating the polythenes, plastics poisoned waste foods from the solid wastes deposited sites.

Industries are a big producer of the packed foods, snacks, cookies, soft drinks, juices, liquors, shampoos, soaps, beauty products etc. All items (products) are packed in a polythene which is not degradable in environment. So a huge amount of such types of solid waste is increasing day by day in all cities at alarming rate. Drainage of the cities are found filled by such types of solid waste. In rainy season such types of waste create the problem of blocked the drainage pipe and speared the water in residential areas and creates the problem of transportation. Loss of biodiversity is the result of the demand for

the new landfill sites to deposit the solid waste. The degradation of health of living beings is the main consequence. Toxic substances released by litter spread through the land, water and air. Due to high rate of air pollution in environment the life of the human beings is decreasing rapidly.

Study Area:–

Meerut city is selected to complete the present study. It is the headquarter of the Meerut district. It is situated in north-western Uttar Pradesh in northern India. It is situated 80 km. northeast of the national capital new Delhi and is 480 km. West of the state capital Lucknow. It is the second most populous city in the national capital region. It has covered 450 km² area and situated between 28.9845°N latitude and 77.705956 east longitude.

Research Problem:–

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to find out the impact of solid waste on environment because the level of solid waste generation in the study area is increasing day by day due to urbanization and industrialization. Solid waste management system is very poor in the study area. Untreated solid waste is depositing outside of the city which is creating the problem of environmental degradation at alarming rate.

Objective of study

1. To analyse the sources of the solid waste generation in the Meerut city.
2. To analyse the solid waste management system of the study area.
3. To analyse the impact of solid waste on environment in the study area.
4. To prepare a solid waste management planning to reduce the level of solid waste generation and disposed it.

Review of Literature

Many research scholars have completed their research work on the research problem of solid waste management and its impacts on environment. The research scholar has made an attempt to arrange the review of literature of the research which are related to the impacts of solid waste on environment. Some related research works are given as–

Qdais (2007) presented a paper on “Environmental impact assessment of municipal solid waste landfills: A case study from Jordan.” They analysed that landfills of the municipal solid waste have an adverse impacts on environment. They found the problem of gaseous emissions from the landfill sites in the Jordan city. Alam and Ahmade (2013) discussed about the impact of solid waste on health and the environment. They pointed that urbanisation and population growth are responsible to high increasing rate of solid waste. They focused on the non-treated solid waste and its impact on human health. Waste that is not properly managed, especially excreta and other liquid and solid waste from households and the community. Agarwal, Chaudhary and Singh (2015) analysed about the waste management initiatives in India for human well being. They found that there is an urgent need to waste management to prevent the epidemic and to make each city a healthy city. Waste management plan and a strong implementation is essential in every city in India. Sharma (2018) analysed that the solid waste management is a serious problem in every country. They discussed about the impact of municipal solid waste on human health. They pointed the rate of generation of solid waste in the Indian cities and analysed the living standards of the people. Sweta (2019) presented a research paper on “A research paper on solid waste management.” She analysed the solid waste management technologies and pointed that modern integrated waste disposal is thus the need for time, where as sustainability needs to be incorporated into all materials, taking into account the material supply and demand. Raju (2021) analysed the methods of solid waste management in India cities. They find out that due to high growth of population in urban areas the problem of environmental degradation is increasing day-by-day. Poor management system is responsible for the problem of environmental degradation in urban areas in India.” Untreated solid waste amount is increasing in urban area and generating the environmental problems. Pujara, Govani, Patel and Pathak (2023) analysed quantification of environmental impacts associated with municipal solid waste management in Rajkot city. They found that at present in Rajkot city the solid waste is generated almost 0.2 million tonnes of municipal solid waste annually. They find out the impacts of solid waste on human beings and animals. Different types of gaises are increasing in the atmosphere due to untreated solid waste deposited on the open sites in Rajkot city. Gour and Singh (2023) presented a research paper on “Solid waste management in India : A state-of-the-art review.” They discussed about the current scenario of solid waste management and its challenges. They pointed that inorganic portion is increasing in the solid waste and organic portion is decreasing in the solid waste which is effecting the environment. Kadam (2023) presented a research paper on “Solid waste management. They analysed about the disposal problem of solid waste in Indian cities.” Collection and transportation facilities are present in the Indian cities but disposal sites are very poor here. So the problem of solid waste management is present here. Benjamin, Gideon and Abubakar (2024). Completed a research paper on “Assessment of municipal solid waste generation, management practices and waste-to-

energy potential in Nigeria – A review.” They found that municipal solid waste generation rate is 0.31 kg/person/day to 1.23 kg/person/day. In their research work they found that about 947981358 kwh/year of energy and \$131769409/year as revenue can be obtain from MSW, prominent MSW management practices currently adopted by the people are open dumping, landfill, open burning, street, stream, river dumping, while incineration method is seldom put to practice.

Generation of the Solid Waste by the Households:-

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to collect the primary data from the selected sources about the solid waste generation. On the basis of the sample survey of the 48 houses about the solid waste generation in the study area Meerut city. Per month average generation of the solid waste of each sample household is given below in the following table-

Table-1

Per Day Generation of the Solid Waste in the Residential Area of the Meerut City (October-2024)

Sample Households	High Income Group Household	Medium Income Group Household	Low Income Group Household
	Average Solid Waste Generation (In kg.)	Average Solid Waste Generation (In kg.)	Average Solid Waste Generation (In kg.)
H ₁	1.85	1.20	0.65
H ₂	1.60	1.35	0.80
H ₃	1.90	0.90	1.00
H ₄	2.10	1.10	0.40
H ₅	1.35	1.25	0.55
H ₆	1.80	0.75	0.70
H ₇	2.20	1.05	1.10
H ₈	1.65	1.00	0.90
H ₉	1.95	1.20	0.80
H ₁₀	2.25	1.10	0.60
H ₁₁	2.50	0.60	0.30
H ₁₂	1.45	1.25	0.80
H ₁₃	1.75	0.90	1.10
H ₁₄	2.30	1.40	1.20
H ₁₅	1.70	1.30	1.70
H ₁₆	1.90	1.20	1.25
Mean	1.89	1.10	0.80

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October 2024.

On the basis of the above table we analysed that high income group household is generated average 1.89 kg. solid waste per day in the study area. These 16 high income group households have generated 907.2 kg solid waste in a month. In the present study we found that medium income group of household is generated average 1.10 kg solid waste per day. These 16 medium income group households have generated average 528

kg. solid waste in a month in the study area. In the present study we found that the low income group household has generated solid waste 0.80 kg per day. These selected 16 lower income group households have generated 384.0 kg solid waste in a month. On the basis of the above table, we can say that high income group households are much generator of solid waste than the lower income group households in the study area. Per month average generation of the solid waste by the households is given below in the table–

Table–2
Per month Average Solid Waste Generation in the Sample Households in the Study Area Meerut City (October–2024)

S. No.	Income Group	Sample Households	Average Per H.H./Day	Average Per H.H./Month	Total in kg.
1.	High Income Group Households	16	1.89	56.7	907.20
2.	Medium Income Group Households	16	1.10	33.0	528.0
3.	Low Income Group	16	0.80	24.0	384.0
Total		48	3.79	113.7	1819.20

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October–2024.

On the basis of the sample survey, we found that total 48 sample households generated 1819.20 kg solid waste in October month in 2024 year. These households have not equality in generating the solid waste in the study area due to the per capita income and expenditure. High income group households have high expenditure on the foods and clothes. So these income group has found in much generator of the solid waste in the study area. Low income group has not sufficient income to fulfill the basic requirements so these households are in lower group of solid waste generator in the study area.

Generation of the Solid Waste by the Hospitals:–

To complete the present study the researcher has selected 12 different types of hospital. These are categorised into 3 category high, medium and low income group. The researcher has made an attempt to find out the solid waste generation amount by sample collection of 30 days of the sample hospitals. The average generation of solid waste amount is given below in the table–

Table–3
Per Day Average Generation of the Solid Waste by the Hospitals in the Study Area Meerut City (October–2024)

Sample Hospitals	Solid Waste Generation (in kg.)			Average
	High Income Group Hospitals	Medium Income Group Hospitals	Low Income Group Hospitals	
S ₁	15.64	9.45	5.25	10.11
S ₂	12.15	9.22	4.65	8.67
S ₃	12.25	8.43	5.93	8.87
S ₄	11.32	7.89	5.45	8.22
Mean	12.84	8.75	5.32	8.97

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey, October 2024.

According to the above table, the hospitals are found the high generation sources of the solid waste. High income group hospital is generated 12.84 kg solid waste per day and medium income group hospital is generated 8.75 kg solid waste per day in the study area Meerut city. Low income group hospital is generated 5.32 kg solid waste per day in the study area. Per day average generation of solid waste has found 8.97 kg per hospital in the study area. In the present study we found that large hospital is generating 385.20 kg solid waste per month in the study area. Medium scale hospital is generating 262.50 kg solid waste per month and low income group hospital is generating 159.60 kg solid waste per month in the study area. In the present study we found that high income group hospitals have better management of the solid waste than the low income group hospitals. They use different types of bins to collect the solid waste but low income group have not use different types of bins to collect the solid waste in the study area.

Generation of the Solid Waste by the Hotels:-

To complete the present study the researcher has selected the hotels as a solid waste generator in sampling. The researcher has selected 12 hotels to collect the primary data related to the solid waste generation in the present study. The researcher has divided the sample hotels into 3 categories that is high, medium and low income group. In the present study the researcher has found that high income group hotels are much generator of the solid waste due to high frequency of the customers and the maintained the quality of the foods and drinking water. The generation of the solid waste by the different types of hotels is given below in the table-

Table-4

Per Day Average Generation of the Solid Waste by the Hotels in the Meerut City (October-2024)

Sample Hotels	Per Day Generation of the Solid Waste (in kg.)			
	High Income Group Hotel	Medium Income Group Hotel	Low Income Group Hotel	Total
S ₁	15.03	13.47	9.87	38.37
S ₂	17.70	15.20	10.62	43.52
S ₃	18.85	11.38	7.65	37.88
S ₄	21.88	10.55	5.73	38.16
Mean	18.37	12.65	8.47	157.93

Source: Computed by the author on the basis of the sample survey.

On the basis of the above table, we find out that high income group hotel is generating average solid waste 18.37 kg/day in the study area, medium income group hotel 12.65 kg per day and low income group hotel is generating 8.47 kg solid waste per day in the study area. All 12 sampled hotels are generating 157.93 kg solid waste per day in the study area. These sampled hotels has generated 4737.90 kg solid waste in the study area in a month. In the present study we found that solid waste management plan is very poor in the hotels. They collected it and transported it but have not treatment techniques. So all types of solid waste are deposited in open plots and sites. So many environmental problems are generated here due to untreated solid waste deposited.

Population Growth in Meerut City:-

Rapid population growth is the result of the high birth rate, low death rate and the migration of the people in the study area. Urbanisation and industrialisation sprawled the geographical area of the study area Meerut city. It is more developed city in the Western Uttar Pradesh. The population was 4.42 lakh of Meerut city in 1981. It was 7.53 lakh in 1991, and 11.61 lakh in 2001 in Meerut city. It was 14.20 lakh in 2011 and 16.97 lakh in 2021 in the Meerut city. During in this period the population growth is found very high in the study area. The growth of the population of Meerut city is given below in the table-

Table-5

Population Growth in Meerut city (1981-2021)

Year	1981	1991	2001	2011	2021
Population	442405	753778	1161716	1420902	1697000
Decadal Growth	-	70.38	54.12	22.31	19.43

Source: 1. Census of India, 1981, 1991, 2001 and 2011

2. Nagar Nigam Meerut Directory, 2021.

According to the above table, we found that the population of the Meerut city was 4.42 lakh in 1981 it has become 16.97 lakh in 2021. During in this period the growth of population was 283.36% in the study area. The population growth was 70.38% in 1981-1991, 54.12% in 1991-2001, 22.31% in 2001-2011 and 19.43% in 2011-2021 in the study area. So this is a big source of solid waste generation in the study area.

Solid Waste Management in Residential Area:-

At present every city is facing the problem of solid waste management. The population of the cities is increasing day by day but the technology is not increasing about the solid waste management. So for dumping mixed waste in landfills has been a key part of India's waste management strategy but landfills emit methane gas. The fumes of landfill gas when inhaled cause respiratory problems especially in children. The residential waste have organic, inorganic, hazardous and inert waste. The work of solid waste management in residential areas is provided by the municipality corporation. This authority collected the solid waste door to door in the residential areas by using the different types of vehicles. At present we observed that the large community bins are provided to the society to collect the solid waste of their houses. The work of sweeping of the streets and roads is completed by the municipalities workers. Such types of solid waste is also collected by the municipality workers by using the rickshaw and motor vehicles. Many types of vehicles are used to collect and transport of the solid waste in the study area. After collected and transported of the solid waste it is deposited in the deposited sites. So we can say that collection, transportation and deposition work is done by the municipality, corporation of Meerut city in the study area.

Solid Waste Management in Hospitals:-

In the present study the researcher has made an attempt to analyse the management systems of the solid waste in the hospitals in the study area Meerut city. We found that high income groups of hospitals have proper collection dustbins to collect the solid waste which is generated by the health facilities. A particular place is provided here to collect all types of waste in the hospitals. They use different types of bins to collect it. After collected it they handover it to the municipality vehicles. Municipality vehicles are transported it and deposited it out side of the city in an open areas by without using any treatment. So a lot of problems are generated by untreated medical waste in the environment general waste, pathological waste, infectious waste, chemical waste, radio active waste, pharmaceutical wastes pressurized container and genotoxic waste etc. are the example of the hospitals waste. Due to examination of the medical waste we found that 62% medical general waste, 23% infectious hazardous waste, 12% non-degradable medical waste and 3% bio-medical sharp. In the present study, we found that the management system of the medical waste collection, segregation, transportation and treatment. Low income group of hospital have not better management of the solid waste in the study area. They are collected all wastage in a large bin and handover it to the municipality vehicles.

Solid Waste Management in Hotels:-

Due to urbanisation the demand of the outing food is increasing day by day. So the hotels and restaurant are developing here in a alarming rate. These hotels and restaurants are the big generators of the solid waste in the metropolitan cities in India. They have not proper management of the solid waste. They collected it and handover to the municipality. All types of waste like that foods, water bottles, disposal glasses, plates, spoons, papers, plastics etc. are found in the hotel generated waste. Methods of

segregation are not followed here. All wet waste are collected in a bin and transported it by rickshaw for deposited the open sites or spaces. Mostly hotels are used only one bin to collect the waste. Very few hotels are used different colours of bins to collect the waste. Mostly hotels have not disposal technology of the collected solid waste. These hotels are collected properly the solid waste and transported it but have not suitable disposal sites. So due to deposited untreated hotel waste many environmental problems are generated around the deposited sites.

The collection work of solid waste in hotels has found regularly in high income group hotels here although and transportation work of the waste has found twice a week. Deposition of hotel waste is usually applied open areas, plots, places and sites etc. Disposal work has found very low level to management of the solid waste by the generation of the hotels.

Impact of the Solid Waste on Environment:-

Due to unsuitable technology related to the solid waste disposal and treatment many environmental problems has increased on the earth. Waste breaks down in landfills to form methane, change in climate, air pollution, water pollution, degradation of the quality of land and biodegradation etc. are the major impacts are found on environment of the solid waste. Plastics, polythene, food wrapping paper, soft drink bottles, cane etc. waste are increasing day by day due to urbanisation and the adoption of the western food culture. Such types of solid waste generate the many harmful gases which are broken the ecosystems and effected the environment. Cholera and infectious are the result of the untreated waste deposit at the residential areas. Untreated waste also effected the animals which animals take food from the heap of waste. They are loosing the immunity and life due to take poisoned food from the solid waste deposited sites. Underground and surface water is loosing the quality of potable water due to the lack of disposal technology of the municipality solid waste. Such types of waste is deposited in Lohiya Nagar in the study area. At this site the level of air and water pollution is found very high. Many women and children are found under the infections diseases due to collecting the plastics, iron, papers, tin and other articles from the heap of the solid waste. They are collected it for their livelihood and earning. Mostly people are found throwing the solid waste into the water bodies. Such types of the waste effected the water bodies ecosystems.

Methodology

To complete the present study the researcher has used both types of data. Primary data has been collected by using the questionnaire method and personal interview. Door to door collection methods of the solid waste is used to find out the result of the research problem. The researcher has made an attempt to find the solid waste generation sources in the study area by field survey. Secondary data related to the solid waste has collected from the various offices, departments, research journals, Ph.D. thesis, magazines and websites etc. The researcher has made an attempt to represent the data by using the tabulation and graphical methods.

Sampling

Randomly sampling method has used to collect the primary data. On the basis of the following sources of the generation of solid waste the researcher has made an attempt to find out the result.

S.No.	Selected Sample	Total Sample	H.I.G.	M.I.G.	L.I.G.
1.	Households	48	16	16	16
2.	Hospitals	12	4	4	4
3.	Hotels	12	4	4	4
Total		72	24	24	24

The researcher has made an attempt to collecting the sample on the basis of the high income group, medium income group and lower income group. There has been collected 72 sample from the 3 sources of solid waste generation. Houses, hospitals and hotels are the selected sample sources of the solid waste generation to complete the present study.

Conclusion

In the present study the researcher has found that mostly solid waste generator sources have not disposal technology of it. They are depositing it without treatment in the open areas. In the present study we found that the deposit sites of the solid wastes have a big issue of air and water pollution. Impact of per capita income is found here in the

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generation of the solid waste from the households. High income group household generating rate of solid waste is found 1.89 kg per day in the study area and medium income group household generating rate of solid waste is found 1.10 kg per day. Although it is found very low 0.80 kg per day in low income group families. Hospitals are a big generator of the solid waste in the study area. Health facilities are present here in a large number. Size of hospital, no. of beds capacity and the facilities are also responsible to the generation of the solid waste in the study area. High income group hospitals are a huge generator of the solid waste. They are generating average 12.84 kg/day/solid waste in the study area, although medium scale hospital generation rate of solid waste is found 8.75 kg per day and low scale income group hospital solid waste rate is found 5.32 kg per day in the study area. Hotels and restaurants are generating solid waste in a big amount in the study area. They have not disposal management of it. In the present study we found that high income group hotel generation rate of solid waste is 18.37 kg per day and medium income group hotel 12.65 kg per day. Low income group of hotel the rate of solid waste generation is found 8.47 kg per day in the study area Meerut city. Due to number of visitors and customers in the hotels and restaurants the difference in generation of solid waste is found here between the high income group and low income group hotels and restaurants. Poorly management of the solid waste is generating the problem of respiratory problems, tuberculosis, cancer, infections diseases.

Suggestions for the future Study The researcher has made an attempt to planning about the reduce the level of solid waste generation. Some methods will be helpful in solid waste management which are present here.

1. Suggestions for Residential Generated Solid Waste Management–

(i) Collect all household waste properly in the personal different types of dustbins according to the solid waste characteristics.

(ii) Separate it properly in the form of useable and not useable on the stage of household.

(iii) Community bins should be established in the society to collect the streets, roads and households waste on the basis of the numbers of households.

(iv) Roads, streets, parks and drainage system should be clean every day and generated solid wastes by its collected in the community bins.

(v) Community bins should be transported twice in a week for unloading.

(vi) People should be taken responsibility to deposit the solid waste in the community bins and prevent the solid waste litter anywhere.

(vii) Biodegradable solid waste should be collected into a pit for prepared the composite manures.

(viii) Reduce the use of single use plastics and papers.

(ix) Reuse materials should be collected into the different types of bins on the primary stage.

2. Suggestions for Hospitals Waste Management of the Solid Waste–

(i) Collection and segregation work of the solid waste should be done on the primary stage.

(ii) Collected solid waste should be transported regularly for the disposal sites.

(iii) Hazardous material should be dumped in a big pit for save the environmental life.

(iv) Reduce, reuse and recycling methods should be used in every hospitals and health facilities centers.

(v) Advanced technology based disposal sites should be established for the health facilities generated waste in the study area.

(vi) Controlled on litter the untreated solid waste into the open sites and drainage.

3. Suggestion for the management of the hotels generated solid waste–

(i) Accept the concept of minimum resources and maximum utilization of it in every hotels.

(ii) Don't waste the food.

(iii) Collected all waste food for the animals.

(iv) Don't use plastics in the excess quantity.

(v) Biodegradable materials should be collected regrettably for organic composite.

(vi) Disposal sites should be established for the treatment of the hotel generated solid waste.

(vii) Aware about the customers about the save water and save resources.

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